

EMODnet: Expanding the EU *in situ* marine data service offer for the Arctic

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EMODnet

European Marine
Observation and
Data Network

The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) is the European Union's *in situ* marine data service. Implemented by a large **network of experts** spanning 133 partner organisations from 33 countries and involving more than 600 contributors from 75 countries, EMODnet's operational service is a trusted source of *in situ* marine environmental and human activities **data and data products** from the coast to open ocean and from European regional sea-basins to the Arctic and beyond. These are assembled from thousands of individual ocean observation campaigns and harmonised at European scale and beyond, serving a diverse user base across various sectors. EMODnet is central to European - and global - marine knowledge,

supporting EU and wider policy implementation, the Blue Economy, research and innovation and more. EMODnet embodies the EU's **Open Data Directive** and the **FAIR principles**. It is an international success story in data diplomacy, demonstrating Europe's leadership in transparent, open and trusted digital knowledge systems. EMODnet also provides the *in situ* marine data component of the **European Digital Twin Ocean**, where EMODnet's full offer is made available on the cloud together with satellite data and modelling capability from the **Copernicus Marine Service**, as part of **EDITO**, the core infrastructure of the European DTO.

The [EMODnet Portal](#) (Figure 1) is a single access point to all EMODnet services, providing open, easy and free access to a wealth of marine data, metadata, and data products. EMODnet's service offer spans **more than sixty-five parameters across the entire marine environment from coast to open ocean, surface to deep seafloor**, while also offering data and information on the Blue Economy operations, from vessel density and offshore platform sitings, and hosting EU Member State Maritime Spatial Plans. EMODnet's service offering of *in situ* marine data and data products spans **seven thematic areas: bathymetry, biology, chemistry, geology, human activities, physics and seabed habitats**. EMODnet also includes a **metadata catalogue**, an **ERDDAP and GeoServer instances**, a **data ingestion service**, marine data expert **networking opportunities** and **training/capacity sharing** activities.

Figure 1: The EMODnet Portal (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/>)

EMODnet for the Arctic

EMODnet already gives an extensive collection of data for the European sector of the Arctic, working together with multiple leading institutes and international initiatives. However, there is great opportunity and potential to expand that coverage with inclusion of data from across the Arctic. This would strengthen EMODnet's service and wider polar marine knowledge for many users in the Arctic and beyond.

EMODnet currently offers various data layers and data products with Arctic coverage (Figures 2 and 3), including ocean physics, marine geology, biology, chemistry and bathymetry. EMODnet offers data visualisation through its Map Viewer, including with Arctic Polar Stereographic (EPSG:3996) projection. The Arctic Ocean remains data scarce compared to most European regional sea-basins.

Figure 2: Screenshot from EMODnet’s Map Viewer, with example of Sea Temperature Anomaly and Observing Platforms data in the Arctic

Figure 3: Screenshot from EMODnet’s Map Viewer, with example of coverage with Bathymetric Surveys in the Arctic, inter alia cooperating with International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean (IBCAO)

The ambition to strengthen EMODnet's service offer in key domains, including polar regions, is detailed in the [EMODnet Community Vision 2035](#) (see Summary and full versions). **By 2035, EMODnet aims to deliver a world-class operational EU capability for FAIR *in situ* Arctic data on oceans, coasts and marine cryosphere**, with integrations of atmospheric and meteorological data, interoperable with the Copernicus Marine Service Arctic Hub, supporting EU and global climate and ocean assessments. To realise this Vision and better serve producers and users of Arctic marine data, **EMODnet recognises the need to significantly increase and expand its equitable engagement and collaborations with Arctic rights holders and stakeholders**. This includes Arctic Indigenous organisations and representatives, local communities and knowledge holders, alongside science and observing communities, policymakers, public agencies, and Blue Economy actors.

EMODnet's service has been rooted in its **core principles** since its inception: Public service; Open Data Sharing; Interoperability; Trust, transparency and provenance; and Open-source solutions and knowledge sharing. EMODnet's envisioned service evolution in the Arctic will be guided by these core principles along with consideration of any appropriate **Arctic-specific guidelines, principles and best practices**, to ensure the ethical and equitable development of its service. Interaction with bodies such as the Arctic Data Committee will be key to realising the service evolution foreseen in its Vision 2035. Strengthening EMODnet's engagement with Arctic rights holders and stakeholders, including data providers, users and managers, and existing Arctic data systems and services, will ensure its service offer is relevant, useful and equitable for users in the Arctic and beyond.